

Conceptualising Authority in a Technologized World

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Abstract

The study analyses the concept of teacher authority and its transformation in the context of an information-technology-driven society and the development of artificial intelligence and new forms of cooperation, communication, and problem solving from the perspective of the philosophy of education. It shows that today's key issues cannot be solved by the concept of a strong traditional leader as a Greek mythical hero, but that it is necessary to understand teachers as authorities in a completely new perspective.

Keywords

artificial intelligence; authority; education; digital world; leader; identity; information society; personality; philosophy of education; responsibility; teacher; teaching; technology; the role of schools

Introduction

The transformation of the concept of authority is the subject of research by several contemporary sociologists and philosophers (Bauman 2013, 2005; Elliott 2009). On the one hand, we see a demand for a clear, understandable leader who knows what to do in all circumstances and resembles an ancient hero. This romanticised view of authority was strongly shaped in the 19th and 20th centuries by the development of romanticism on the one hand and the growing complexity of society and the world on the other. In this respect, authority simplifies the world and makes it safer. At the same time, however, we can see the growing complexity of the world, which does not allow individuals to make independent decisions, because the problems they encounter are too complex, require new perspectives, and can only be understood through dialogue. Science, technology, and society have become interconnected phenomena of cooperation. And yet, finding a new, comprehensible concept of authority in this situation seems difficult.

In the current education space, there is debate over whether generative AI can replace teachers (Baidoo-Anu and Owusu Ansah 2023). This may be a technocratic neoliberal debate in some respects, but it is also a rational debate in some respects. Large language models can be a valuable resource for personalised learning across many disciplines, yet their “expertise” and

error rate may not be higher than those of a regular live teacher. However, these models do not address the questions this study raises about teacher identity and authority (Condrey 2023).

It is the authority or personality of the teacher that is one of the essential constitutive elements that we have to work with in the philosophy of education. Thus, the key question before us is what form of authority is possible or appropriate to associate with the teacher in a technologized world (Latzer 2022), what kind of teacher they should be. Before proceeding to an answer, it will be necessary to examine three changes (chosen from the two ideal types of authority) that technology brings to the conceptualisation of authority.

The first aspect concerns hyper-objects, as discussed by Bělohradský (2021, 290–8). These are phenomena (services, companies, global problems) that, in their size and complexity, exceed the capabilities of conventional solutions. We live in a world where global climate change has no simple solutions, no one optimal way to approach it. Technology has fundamentally accelerated these phenomena and transformed global power. Bělohradský writes that states no longer have sovereign power but only limited regulatory possibilities. Bridle (2018, chap. 7) speaks of how technology has lost the concept of responsibility, which Heidegger (1967b, 22–4) speaks of life in the drag of technology. At the same time, these hyper-objects constitute a crucial part of the reality in which we find ourselves and must be addressed educationally.

The second important feature is the plane of hyper-connectivity, as described, for example, by Floridi (2014, 23; 2019, 197–212). We are in a world where science, technology, and, increasingly, art are a team effort. Many modern art forms, such as computer game development, movies or virtual reality, require (in principle) collaboration on two planes. People among themselves, which brings into educational discourse the need to think more and deeper about collaboration-teaching, as currently conceived, is too individualistic in its methods (teaching methodology), forms of assessment, and topic design. The second aspect of hyper-connectivity is collaborating with technology (Floridi 2014), using artificial intelligence and other systems to deliver quality outcomes effectively. In many areas, such as programming, the big question is whether there is any point in teaching without working with it or engaging with AI effectively.

The two examples above show the growing infosphere, the increasingly complex and robust information environment in which humans find themselves. Still, they also dynamically shape themselves and are shaped by them (Floridi 2014, 41). The growth of efficiency, performance and outputs, the need to be always online, to present oneself in a consistently positive light (how one has the perfect figure, breakfast, work, how much one has accomplished at work or what one has learned) in a connected environment not only leads to higher work productivity, but also to several negative aspects. The circadian world is experiencing a pandemic of depression and depressive feelings, but also an increase in many other mental illnesses and problems that cannot be hidden under the optimistic view of better diagnostics (West 2023). We seem to be able to promote productivity in the short term, not the long term.

Thus, a third feature may be, on the one hand, the increasing pressure and complexity of the world (negative view) or, on the positive side, a distinctly shaped emphasis on digital wellbeing (Smits et al. 2022). This is defined by the National Institute of Education as follows:

Digital well-being is a state in which we recognise the benefits and risks of using digital technologies in current conditions. Based on this, we integrate digital technologies into our lives to support our overall health, personal development, and our responsibility towards ourselves, our environment, and the world. (NPI ČR 2025)

It can be said to be the ability not to be in the tow of technology, to relegate it to the position of a tool, to have a certain freedom. It is not about convenience or comfort, but a form of attunement to the self, the ability to live in a complex and dynamic world in a way that does not degenerate into Kahneman's System 1, a binary oppositional thought structure (Kahneman 2011, 19–22), which is often manifested by nationalism, the desire to reject technology altogether, or xenophobia.

If we look at these three levels of phenomena through the lens of authority models, we can see the possibilities each model offers. The model of authority as a strong leader or hero fails with hyper-objects because it cannot handle complex situations in a differential way. It is also why many of the political elites, says Latour (2018, chap. 12), fail: people demand this model of authority but want them to solve hyper-object problems.

In the case of the hyper-connected world, he can be surprisingly successful; on the one hand, he may not offer the capacity for deep collaboration, but at the same time, through his story and charisma, he creates a network of indirect participants around him, becoming a celebrity or an influencer (Han and Balabanis 2024; Bauman 2013), a person who has influence precisely because he is embedded in a system of informational interactions of the connected world.

In digital wellbeing, a model of a strong, unchanging leader who always offers clear solutions is placed in a state of ambivalence. On the one hand, he does not admit weakness and problems, creating a form of self-narrative that makes him resistant to the threat of a complex dynamic world; on the other hand, he creates what Damasio (2018, chap. 3) refers to as a delicate balance – an equilibrium. An equilibrium that can be a source of resilience, but its collapse usually has quite fatal consequences.

We need to find a new model of authority based on inherent weakness, fragmentation, limitations, and cooperation. Our world is too complex for uncooperative “heroes” and “strong, decisive leaders”. Appears to be possible in hyper-objects because it does not presuppose fixed, pre-given solutions, but is willing to negotiate, adapt and cooperate. It is thus able to be part of a πόλις that is not a set of ιδιώτης, isolated private individuals, but a broadly participating informational organism (Damasio 2018, chap. 10).

A paradoxical situation arises in hyper-connectedness, where on the one hand the search for new perspectives and models, together with the ability to connect with others, constitutes a specific “effective skill”, but does not lead to a model of strong mythological self-narrative; such an authority is a worker of everyday life, a man of small everyday honest work, but not that visible personality, a star, a person to whom others will look up to.

What kind of authority do we need in education?

The key question we now face is what we expect from the teacher's authority in a changing society. The answer to this question should be reflected in teacher training, teacher formation and the broader debate about what courses, methods, and approaches we can use in education. We cannot have a general discussion about schooling and authority here. However, we will try to relate it to the current situation in the context of global technological transformation. It is undeniable that:

- 1) Digital technologies are part of students' everyday experience in an occidental cultural circle. These technologies have advantages and disadvantages, but they are part of the world that shapes students' epistemic and axiological fields. It is impossible to exclude the digital revolution or the digital world from reflecting on the philosophy of education. The boundary between the technical world and the world of direct sensory human experience, as discussed by the phenomenologists (Patočka 1992, 13–17), no longer exists; we inhabit one onlife environment of the infosphere (Floridi 2014).
- 2) Our world has never been more complicated and complex, requiring such a degree of collaboration, abstract thinking or new competencies. The sense of a changing world has been around for a long time, but what is new is the transformation affecting the very fabric of ontological reality (Downes 2008; Latour 2007).
- 3) From the data on students' mental health, we can conclude that the increasing pressure and uncertainty associated with the inhabited space pose a significant challenge for education.

It is possible to say that schools can and should play the role of specific landmarks in this concept (in astrophysics, the term standard candle is used – an object of known luminosity allowing one to easily measure the distance of this object from the Earth, thus orienting oneself in distances and topology). The question is whether such a role is even possible. Whether we use the CYNEFIN model (Hasan and Kazlauskas 2014), we do not live in a world where manifest situations form an increasingly less substantial part of the epistemic field.

Let us think about the authority of the teacher. We must necessarily look for a model that will be an authority not in the field associated with the structure of the world, as Obvious and Complicated, which is usually the educational curricular focus, but in the field of Complex. We consider this shift in the conceptualisation of authority to be fundamental. We need education to be carried by the capacity for critical thinking – that is, discerning our situation, what we can know about it, and how we can relate to it, as well as reflecting on them.

A model of a strong leader who always offers clear solutions as an authoritative teacher of myths is inauthentic, however appealing it may be. It can be described as one of the temptations of contemporary pedagogy. We can make the teacher into an authoritative leader whom students will follow and admire, who is never wrong or falters, and who has a clear idea (Obvious World) of what should and should not happen. This simplification of the world may lead to a sense of security, but it is fickle, built on a simplistic narrative and simple instruments

that you “have to use”. Many of the virtues of rigid modernity fundamentally do not work in liquid modernity (Bauman 2013).

The challenges of the world we find ourselves in are so different that we need to change our perspective radically (Latour 2021, chap. 3), to enter the space of uncertainty that the teacher will share with the students. In this radical openness in participation in a shared world, we believe the authenticity of authority emerges. Authority not as a definitive fixed unchanging static answer (*veritas*), often sounded before the questions, but rather a sharing of a standard process of uncovering the unhidden (*ἀλήθεια*); if we take Heidegger’s classification of approaches to (Heidegger 1967a, § 44).

The approach to knowledge as *veritas* expects predefined forms that enable a charismatic leader to structure their program; *veritas* serves as the training foundation upon which AI engines can be built. However, in a world of mutability and complexity, this fixed, predetermined knowledge constitutes only a part of the basis for decision-making. A charismatic leader operates under the conviction that this wellspring of fixed and unchanging truth describes the world in which we live. As we have shown, however, a substantially deeper and more adequate description of reality is linked to the concept of non-concealment – a concept that cannot be possessed, one that must always be re-examined in light of what we can learn about the world and ourselves. The concept of *ἀλήθεια* is the path of humility, which makes possible a new concept of authority.

It seems – based on the analysis made – that it is possible to use selected elements of the traditional concept of authority, because there is a certain degree of truth and justification in them (as in the Trinitarian heresies, after all). However, we must get used to a new kind of authority more closely associated with the concept of Gregor Samsa (Kafka 2004; Latour 2021). An authority that is carried by the words of Jesus: “Take my yoke upon you and learn from me, for I am meek and lowly in heart” (Matt 11:29). In Matthew Jesus is the archetype of an authority figure who does not need to draw attention to himself, who does not have ready-made, universal solutions for everything, regardless of context. Jesus’ truth is *ἀλήθεια*, not *veritas*, which is reflected in the way he exercises his authority.

This noiselessness of authority turns to the earth, to the reflection of what is essential, and represents one of the crucial moments in the constitution of a newly understood authority (Latour 2018). Not as an authority of power and fear, or of the fascination with “charisma”, but rather a balanced, empathetic one, someone who makes available to the other a view of his face, not as a mask, but as a vulnerable offer of relationality (Levinas 2011; Buber 2017).

It is this aspect of authority, which does not go the way of easy shortcuts, that we also consider crucial in our reflection, as it will enable us to teach students to resist the lure of simplistic leaders, charismatic politicians, and preachers. Herakles (as the archetype of traditional authority) hides behind his position of strength and courage a weakness in discernment, questioning his decisions, a fear that dependence on others will rob him of his exceptionalism. Indeed, Greek mythology suggests that this notion of authority is problematic – it plunges one

into revenge and suspicion and does not lead to peace. It is a fragment of life with no openness to the whole, against which it can become isolated.

Conclusion

The study attempted to analyse the context of a technologized society about the reconceptualisation of the phenomenon of authority in education. We consider the transformation of the educator's understanding as a charismatic individualistic leader to be fundamental, as this concept of authority is unsustainable in the long term and does not allow for the education of democratic citizens of the information society in their authentic engagement with a specific new type of authority. This new type requires a fundamental rethinking of humanity as beings with limitations, vulnerabilities, a need for others, and a strong environmental anchoring, with the ability to discern. The study shows that precisely this type of authority makes it possible to solve the problems of the hyper-connected world (Floridi 2014, 23) and the hyper-objects (Bělohradský 2021, 290) within it, and that it is of fundamental importance to strive for it among teachers, as key actors in education.

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